

CYCLIC BEHAVIOUR OF FIBREGLASS-EPOXY COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of experimental tests conducted to determine the tensile fatigue performance of cross-ply $[\pm 45]_{5s}$ and multidirectional $[-45_2 +45_2 0_2]_s$ fibreglass-epoxy laminates. The parameters varied in these tests were the frequency of loading and laminate lay-up.

For the cross-ply laminates, the test results show that there is significant cyclic creep which depends on loading condition, i.e. applied load and frequency. In contrast, relatively small cyclic creep was observed for multidirectional laminates. The effect of frequency on cyclic creep and fatigue life is presented and discussed.

Keywords: cyclic loads, composite materials, fatigue life, cyclic creep, frequency effects.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fibre-reinforced plastic (FRP) materials are extensively used in many engineering fields including the transportation, civil engineering and chemical industries. They offer a number of advantages over conventional materials including superior corrosion resistance, reduced weight and improved fatigue properties. One of the largest groups of FRP materials are fibreglass-epoxy composites.

Due to their highly anisotropic nature, FRP materials show a rather complex damage behaviour under cyclic loading, e.g. matrix cracking, fibre-matrix debonding, delamination, void growth and fibre breakage [1-3]. These various damage mechanisms usually do not combine to form a single dominant crack, which grows in a self-similar manner as in the case of metals. Moreover, the fatigue behaviour of fibre/matrix composite systems are often rate (frequency) sensitive [4,5].

Most of the presently used methods for life prediction of FRP materials are of an empirical nature. In order to better understand the relationship between laminate lay-up and rate (frequency)-dependent fatigue behaviour of FRP materials, more experimental data is needed.

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It is the objective of this paper to study experimentally the effects of frequency on the tensile fatigue performance of cross-ply $[\pm 45]_{5s}$ and multidirectional $[-45_2 +45_2 0_2]_s$ fibreglass-epoxy laminates.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experimental test specimens were manufactured using "Scotchply" type 1003 unidirectional prepreg tape which contained continuous filament "E" type glass fibers embedded in epoxy resin (resin content $36 \pm 3\%$ by weight). The test specimens were fabricated by hand cutting and lay-up into a specially designed mold unit. The cross-ply $[\pm 45]_{5s}$ samples consist of a total of 20 layers (0.254 mm thick) of alternating $+45^\circ$ and -45° fiber orientations symmetric with respect to the midplane. The multidirectional $[-45_2 +45_2 0_2]_s$ specimens consist of a total of 12 layers (0.254 mm thick) with the lay-up alternating in pairs between 0° , $+45^\circ$ and, finally, -45° on the outside, symmetrically with the midplane.

The cross-ply samples were cured at 150°C for 12 hours. The void content of the cross-ply samples was found to be $\sim 3\%$. In order to reduce the void content in multidirectional specimens, a "vacuum stripping" operation was performed. Once lamination had been completed the multidirectional lay-up was put into a vacuum environment at < 1.3 Pa for 18 hours. Following vacuum stripping, the mold and lay-up were placed in an oven preheated to 235°C for curing. When the temperature of the mold reached 160°C (gel point), a pressure of 690 kPa was applied to the lay-up. After a one hour cure time at 160°C the mold was allowed to cool in the oven to room temperature.

Substantial improvement in the reduction of void content (below 1%) was obtained by utilizing the above mentioned vacuum stripping procedure. After curing, the thicknesses of cross-ply (20 ply) and multidirectional (12 ply) laminates were 4.75 ± 0.05 mm and 2.95 ± 0.05 mm, respectively. The width and length of all specimens were 12.85 ± 0.1 mm and ~ 200 mm, respectively. Aluminum tabs were glued to the ends of the samples to facilitate gripping.

Uniaxial fatigue tests were carried out at room temperature with a load ratio $R = P_{\min}/P_{\max} \approx 0.05$. The loading system employed was an electro-hydraulic servo-controlled MTS unit. Two frequencies of load cycle with sinusoidal wave form were used: a low frequency, 0.417 Hz (25 cpm), and a high frequency, 3.33 Hz (200 cpm). In the case of cross-ply laminates the actual high frequency was 3.6 Hz (217 cpm). Except for the low frequency/cross-ply laminate tests, an IBM PC computer was used to provide a command signal and to record the data from the load cell and a 25.4 mm gauge length extensometer. For the low frequency/cross-ply laminate tests, a command signal was provided by the MTS function generator and the data was recorded on an X-Y plotter.

The fatigue loads were preselected as a percentage of the monotonic failure load. Three monotonic breaking tests were carried out for each lay-up investigated. The average values of the monotonic failure stresses, S_f , and an initial axial elastic moduli, E_o , were: $S_f = 203$ MPa, $E_o = 10\,070$ MPa and $S_f = 351$ MPa, $E_o = 18\,200$ MPa for cross-ply and multidirectional laminates, respectively.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Cross-Ply Laminate

Fatigue test results, for both frequencies investigated, are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Fatigue Test Results of $[\pm 45]_5$ Laminate

f = 0.417 Hz Tests		f = 3.6 Hz Tests	
Normalized Max. Stress, σ_{\max}/S_f	Cycles to Failure, N_f	Normalized Max. Stress, σ_{\max}/S_f	Cycles to Failure, N_f
0.500	2 552	0.480	2 813
0.421	17 730	0.427	8 578
0.365	62 500	0.345	136 508
0.322	168 100	0.321	702 984

The cyclic stress-strain diagram obtained for specimen C1 is shown in Figure 1. For this relatively high stress, $\sigma_{\max} = 101.4$ MPa (~ 50% of monotonic strength), the cross-ply laminate exhibits significant cyclic creep and a moderate hysteresis loop. It is seen that at the unloading point the stress-strain curve does not follow an elastic path, but instead bends forward. This indicates the presence of a viscous strain. A significant cyclic creep, i.e. accumulated strain, ϵ , with number of cycles, N , was observed. Computed values of the cyclic creep rate, $d\epsilon/dN$ versus

Figure 1 Stress-strain response of cross-ply laminate under cyclic loading

the life ratio, N/N_f for both frequencies are shown in Figure 2. The rate of cyclic creep is initially high, it then decreases sharply towards an approximately steady value, and subsequently increases to a high rate just before final fracture. At higher stress levels the cyclic creep rate is higher for the 3.6 Hz tests than for the slower ones. On the other hand, at lower stress levels, this trend is reversed. This indicates that the rate of cyclic creep depends on both frequency and applied stress. All the curves in Figure 2 exhibit a characteristic wide "U" shape. This signifies that each specimen is subjected to an approximately steady rate of cyclic creep for most of its life.

The degradation of apparent cyclic elastic modulus upon reloading, E_c , was also investigated. The change in modulus can be related to the combined internal damage of the material [6]. The variation of the normalized elastic modulus versus life ratio for the high frequency tests, $f = 3.6$ Hz, is shown in Figure 3. A general response in the decay of normalized modulus with increasing life ratios is seen. An initial rapid decay of the apparent cyclic modulus is noted. Similar trends in the degradation of the cyclic modulus were observed for the low frequency tests, i.e. $f = 0.417$ Hz. It is interesting to note that the rate of degradation of cyclic moduli follow the same trend as the rate of cyclic creep (compare Figures 2 and 3).

Figure 2 Variation of cyclic creep rate versus life ratio

Figure 3 Cyclic degradation of normalized elastic modulus versus life ratio

The relationship of normalized maximum stress versus the number of cycles to failure for both frequencies is shown in Fig. 4a. The normalized maximum stress versus the steady rate of cyclic creep is depicted in Fig. 4b for both frequencies. It is noted that the best fit fatigue life lines, corresponding to the slow and fast tests, cross-over. The detrimental influence of the cyclic creep on fatigue life of the cross-ply laminate is evident from examining Figure 4.

Figure 4 Normalized maximum stress versus (a) number of cycles to failure, (b) steady rate of cyclic creep

3.2 Multidirectional Laminate

The fatigue test results of the multidirectional specimens, for both frequencies, are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Fatigue Test Results of $[-45_2 +45_2 0_2]_s$ Laminate

Normalized Max. Stress, σ_{\max}/S_f	Cycles to Failure, N_f ($f = 3.3$ Hz Tests)	Cycles to Failure, N_f ($f = 0.417$ Hz Tests)
0.859	551 752	231 1 786
0.763	2 883 4 209	2 795 2 897
0.668	16 890 31 004	- -
0.572	136 350 284 973	105 194 -

In Figure 5 these results are plotted in terms of the normalized maximum stress versus the number of cycles to failure. In contrast to the cross-ply laminates, no noticeable frequency effect on fatigue life is seen, and a single best-fit line appears to describe the results fairly well. In addition, no significant cyclic creep was observed due to the constraining action of the 0° plies. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is no significant frequency effect in the multidirectional specimens due to the lack of cyclic creep.

Figure 5 Normalized maximum stress versus number of cycles to failure for multidirectional laminates

4. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental research program has been conducted to examine the influence of lay-up and frequency on the fatigue behaviour of fibreglass-epoxy laminates.

The loading frequency had a significant effect on the tensile fatigue performance of cross-ply $[\pm 45]_s$ laminate. This effect is explained in terms of cyclic creep and its detrimental influence on the fatigue life of the material. At lower stresses the cyclic creep increases and the fatigue life decreases with reduced loading frequency. In contrast, at higher stresses, the fatigue life decreases and the cyclic creep increases with higher frequency.

In the case of the multidirectional $[-45_2 +45_2 0_2]_s$ laminates, the applied loading frequency did not appear to have any influence on fatigue life since the 0° plies restrain the development of cyclic creep.

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